

Pressure effects on collective density fluctuations in water and protein solutions – Insights from neutron scattering experiments and molecular dynamics simulations

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Abstract

Neutron Brillouin scattering and molecular dynamics simulation have been used to investigate protein hydration water density fluctuations as a function of pressure. Our results show significant differences between the pressure and density dependence of collective dynamics in bulk water and in concentrated protein solutions. Pressure-induced changes in the tetrahedral order of the water hydrogen bond network have direct consequences for the high-frequency sound velocity and damping coefficients, which we find to be a sensitive probe for changes in the hydrogen bond network structure as well as the wetting of biomolecular surfaces.

Keywords: *high pressure, hydration water dynamics, collective THz dynamics, molecular dynamics, neutron scattering*

Introduction

High-pressure effects on protein structure and dynamics are of significant interest in biology, not only to account for the adaptation of life to extreme environments, but also to understand how macromolecules behave under normal conditions¹⁻². Pressure can modulate protein activity³, it may lead to dissociation of oligomeric proteins⁴ and other supermolecular structures⁵, induce⁶ or inhibit⁷⁻⁸ the formation of aggregates and amyloid fibrils, induce denatured states⁹, and modify their solvation¹⁰. High pressure allows to explore different conformational substates, to study folding and unfolding¹¹ and affects the kinetics of enzymatic reactions^{9, 12}. In some cases, high pressure increases the local roughness of the free energy landscape, thus increasing the depth of local minima and stabilizing intermediate states¹³⁻¹⁵. A general feature of pressure-induced effects on protein dynamics is the slowing down of motions and a consequent stiffening and increasing of relaxation times¹³⁻¹⁵.

Moderate, non-denaturing pressures induce an elastic response of solvated proteins, which is mainly associated to compression of the hydration shells and non-bonded inter-atomic distances. The applied pressure modifies the packing and order of the solvent at the protein surface, increases the protein hydration, and promotes the penetration of water in hydrophobic cavities¹⁶⁻¹⁷. This induces swelling and eventually unfolding at pressures sufficient for denaturation¹⁸. Detailed changes in protein hydration at elevated pressures have been observed in molecular dynamics simulations of isolated proteins in solution, i.e. distortion of tetrahedral structure and stiffening of vibrational modes¹⁹.

Detailed comparisons of pressure-induced effects (at moderate non-denaturing pressures ≤ 3 kbar) in protein solutions and the bulk solvent can provide insights into the hydration of proteins. Small-angle X-ray scattering and neutron scattering experiments have been recently combined by Russo and co-workers to investigate high-pressure-induced changes on particle-particle interactions, low-resolution structure and global and local dynamics of lysozyme in aqueous solutions²⁰⁻²². The results showed that lysozyme maintains its globular structure up to at least 1500 bar, while the density of the hydration shell slightly increases as a function of pressure. This causes a moderate nonlinear change in the effective protein-protein interaction potential observed by SAXS measurements^{20, 23}. At the same time, local dynamics described by mean square displacements of the protein protons (measured by quasi-elastic neutron scattering, QENS) decreases as pressure increases, suggesting a loss in protein mobility that may follow an increase of the hydration shell density. Even small volume variations can result in a sizeable change of protein fluctuations. Both global and local protein dynamics change at the same threshold pressure, and for timescales accessible in a QENS experiment (ps), a transition from diffusive internal protein dynamics to localized motions within a local potential energy well has been observed²⁰⁻²¹. This behavior has been attributed to the denser structural packing in the first hydration layer of the solvated proteins at elevated pressure.

A similar behavior can be also found for other examples of biomolecular interfaces²⁴. However, we note that at the same time pressure-induced disruption of the tetrahedral structure of water can speed up local dynamics in protein hydration water, such as translational and rotational diffusion and HB rearrangements^{19, 25-28}. It is important to note though that collective and local single-particle dynamics describe fundamentally different

processes and are not directly related to each other, but represent complementary information. Single-particle dynamics as reported by QENS studies report on atomic mobilities of the non-deuterated fraction of a system, while coherent scattering experiments are sensitive to the propagation of density fluctuations in the entire system due to dynamic correlations in time and space.

To shed light on the impact of pressure on the structure of the protein hydration water hydrogen bond network and its correlation to a general slowdown of protein dynamics, we investigate here the collective dynamics of water in the presence of solvated proteins, combining coherent neutron scattering with computer simulations. Collective dynamics of water on an energy scale of 5 to 30 meV provide direct insights into correlated intermolecular vibrations²⁹⁻³⁰, i.e. propagating density fluctuations in the hydrogen bond network of an aqueous solution. The properties of these modes are sensitive to hydrogen bond network properties and therefore provide an excellent tool to study solute- and pressure-induced changes in water and aqueous solutions. Coherent scattering experiments and molecular dynamics simulations have therefore been used frequently to study collective dynamics in biomolecular solutions and even in living cells or the influence of temperature and/or pressure on the hydrogen bond network of bulk water³⁰⁻³⁷.

Methods

Here, we show for the first time room temperature neutron Brillouin measurements of lysozyme solutions combined with molecular dynamics simulations as a function of pressure. The analysis of experimental results provides a description of *dispersion curves*, defining the active collective modes that propagate within the sample, and the *damping*

factor, related to the propagation lifetimes. The measurements were performed on concentrated solutions of lysozyme (10% w/w) dissolved in D₂O buffer (10 mM Tris, pD=6.0) using the time of flight neutron Brillouin spectrometer BRISP and a titanium alloy large volume, high pressure sample holder (see Supporting Information for experimental details). To obtain information on the protein interface and the contribution of the hydration water layer, both lysozyme solution and neat D₂O were measured at pressures of 1 bar, 2 kbar and 3 kbar. The stability of the protein solutions under the experimentally studied conditions has been established by pressure-denaturation studies in the literature using various experimental probes, including Raman spectroscopy, NMR³⁸ and tryptophane fluorescence³⁹⁻⁴⁰ (see Supplementary Information for more detailed discussion). Molecular dynamics simulations were carried out for bulk water and for solvated lysozyme proteins, in dilute and high concentration conditions (10% w/w), at pressures of 1 bar, 500 bar, 1 kbar, 2 kbar, 3 kbar and 5 kbar, allowing microscopic insights into structural changes in water and the protein hydration shell as a response to pressure (see Supporting Information for simulation details).

At the experimentally studied protein concentration, approximately two thirds of all water molecules are found at distances greater than 10 Å from the protein surface based on our simulation models, suggesting a significant amount of bulk-like water.

Results & Discussion

Figure 1 shows experimental data at four selected wave vectors obtained for the Lysozyme solution at 2 kbar, together with the best fit using a two-component damped harmonic oscillator model (DHO; see Supporting Information for details).

Figure 1. Coherent inelastic spectra of Lysozyme solution at 2 kbar at selected Q -values. The thick black line shows fits of the data with two DHOs model (see Supporting Information for details). The dashed blue and dotted green lines represent the resulting low- and high-frequency DHO, respectively. The dashed-dotted yellow line shows the experimental resolution function.

The dependence of the fitted DHO frequencies on the momentum transfer Q defines the dispersion curves shown in Figure 2. Only the high frequency mode is of dispersive nature and will be discussed in the following paragraphs. Figure 2 shows a comparison of the experimental *dispersion curves* of (A) lysozyme solution and (B) neat D_2O as a function of pressure. Figure 2A further shows a dispersion curve corresponding to measurements on *E. coli* cells at ambient pressure from a previous study³². The pronounced similarity to the concentrated protein solution at the same pressure shows that the collective properties in both samples are comparable. The differences between the collective dynamics in

protein solutions, living cells and bulk water at ambient pressure are statistically significant, but comparably small compared to pressure-induced changes. Considering high water concentrations of up to 80% within the cells⁴¹, this observation would be consistent with largely bulk-like collective properties of water within cells as probed via coherent neutron scattering. From the slope of the linear regime (between $Q = 0.2$ and 1.1 \AA^{-1}), we obtain a propagation velocity of density fluctuations, i.e. the high frequency or fast sound velocity, of $3460 \pm 160 \text{ m/s}$ for the collective excitation in the protein solution at ambient pressure. The corresponding slope of the dispersion curve for neat D_2O is equal to $3040 \pm 50 \text{ m/s}$. Both, the pure water samples and the concentrated protein solutions show a statistically significant increase of the density fluctuation propagation velocity with increasing pressure. For the protein solution, the propagation velocity of the high frequency mode increases to $3730 \pm 180 \text{ m/s}$ and $3920 \pm 210 \text{ m/s}$ at 2 kbar and 3 kbar, respectively. The corresponding propagation velocities in the neat water sample are observed as $3530 \pm 175 \text{ m/s}$ and $3770 \pm 188 \text{ m/s}$ at 2 kbar and 3 kbar.

Figure 2. Experimental dispersion curves of THz collective modes in hydration water of (A) lysozyme solution water network and (B) neat D_2O as a function of pressure (D_2O data for 1 bar from Ref. 42). The

dispersion curve of *E. coli* is reported in (A) for comparison (data from Ref. 32). Error bars are equivalent for measurements at different pressures. For clarity, they are shown only for one respective data set for the protein solution and bulk water.

The comparison between neat water and protein solutions allows us to study differences in pressure-induced changes of collective dynamics in both samples, which are attributed to the presence of the proteins and their interactions with the surrounding hydration water.

At equivalent pressures, the sound propagation velocity in the protein solution is higher compared to bulk water in the studied pressure range (see Figure S2 in Supporting Information), suggesting an increased rigidity of the water hydrogen bond network in the presence of the protein. This interpretation agrees with experimental observations and simulations that observe a slowdown of dynamical processes in the protein hydration shell that require rearrangements of the hydrogen bond network. This applies for example to translational and rotational motions of water molecules as probed by magnetic relaxation dispersion⁴³, nuclear Overhauser effects in reverse micelles⁴⁴, Overhauser dynamic nuclear polarization⁴⁵ and ultrafast fluorescence⁴⁶⁻⁴⁷ to name but a few. Numerous molecular dynamics simulations reproduce these observations⁴⁸⁻⁵¹. The consensus is an up to two-fold dynamical retardation for the majority of water molecules in a protein hydration shell, while only a small number of water molecules might be strongly bound and therefore further immobilized.

In our present study, we find for both samples, bulk water and the protein solution, that propagation velocities further increase with pressure. We note that the increase in the propagation velocity is not the result of an increased rigidity of the water hydrogen bond network as one would define it based non-collective, single-particle dynamics, for example, via lifetimes of individual hydrogen bonds. The pressure-induced distortion of

the water hydrogen bond network structure weakens water-water hydrogen bonds, hence decreasing the average lifetime^{19, 25, 27-28}.

From previous simulations and experiments, it is known that the increase in pressure results in a slowdown of picosecond timescale protein dynamics^{14, 21}, which might be intimately related to pressure-induced changes in the hydration environment. We highlight that the pressure-dependence of the propagation velocity is more pronounced in bulk water than in the protein solution. Consequently, the difference in sound propagation velocities between both systems decreases at high pressure (linear extrapolation of the pressure-dependent experimental data yields equal sound propagation velocities in both systems at ≈ 4.4 kbar (see Figure S2 in Supporting Information for details). Further, the sound propagation velocity in bulk water at 2 kbar (3530 ± 175 m/s) is approximately equivalent to the sound propagation velocity in the protein solution at ambient pressure (3460 ± 160 m/s). This indicates potential similarities of protein-induced and pressure-induced effects on the hydrogen bond network structure of water, which largely determines the collective properties in both samples. An increased density of water in protein hydration shells, which would qualitatively mimic the effect of increased pressure, has been observed experimentally in combined x-ray and neutron scattering experiments⁵².

In addition to changes in collective dynamics, the densities of both samples obviously increase with pressure. For protein solutions, it has been shown that particularly the densities of the hydration layer are strongly pressure dependent²⁰⁻²¹. The density and collective dynamics in fluids are inherently coupled in the Newton-Laplace equation. In Figure 3, we therefore analyze pressure-induced changes of the propagation velocity as a function of the sample density. Due to the lack of experimental densities for pressurized

protein solutions, we obtained the density data from our molecular dynamics simulations of deuterated protein solutions and bulk D₂O.

As comparison, Figure 3 also reports the sound velocity probed for water solvating hydrophilic and hydrophobic protein model interfaces at ambient pressure⁵³. Single-particle vibrations in these solutions at frequencies comparable to the ones studied here in the context of collective dynamics were previously shown to correlate with those of high-density amorphous (HDA) ice and low-density amorphous (LDA) ice, respectively⁵⁴. Therefore, we combined the sound velocities of both samples with the densities of HDA and LDA ice in Fig. 3, observing that they follow the overall observed trend. We note, that the high-density data point (water solvating a hydrophilic surface) is found in close proximity to bulk D₂O at ~2 kbar. Interactions with the hydrophilic model interface at ambient pressure therefore also give rise to qualitatively similar changes in the water hydrogen bond network as found for the protein solution, i.e. they resemble densities and collective dynamics of pressurized water.

Figure 3. Density dependence of the sound velocity of D₂O and lysozyme solution at various pressures. Data obtained for solutions containing large concentrations of hydrophilic and hydrophobic bio-interface are

shown according to Ref. 53. Colors indicate the distinct pressures equivalent to Figure 2. The dashed line serves as a guide to the eye.

The high density region, represented in Figure 3, shows an approximate linear density-dependence of the sound velocity. The plotted data points provide a weak indication that this trend may not hold for densities lower than 1.1 g/cm^3 . We note that Krisch and co-workers observed an anomalous feature in x-ray scattering experiments of H_2O between 1.1 and 1.17 g/cm^3 , i.e. a shoulder in the density dependent sound velocity⁵⁵. The data shown in Figure 3 exhibits a similar behavior, however, the small number of data points and the statistical error bars of the sound velocities, inhibit a direct comparison. Arguably, the feature observed by Krisch *et al.* might be expected at higher densities in our sample due to the use of D_2O in neutron scattering experiments.

Krisch *et al.* also show that the dependence of the low-frequency, hydrodynamic sound velocity on the increasingly distorted hydrogen bond network structure for increasing pressure is more pronounced compared to the high-frequency sound velocity analyzed here⁵⁵. However, our results show that the high-frequency sound velocity is suitable to observe distinct pressure-induced changes in bulk water and protein hydration water due to differences in the structural response upon compression.

Figure 4. Damping factors relative to mode frequency for (A) concentrated lysozyme solution and (B) neat D_2O with increasing pressure. The results for bulk water at 1 bar are reproduced from Ref. 42. For clarity error bars, equivalent for all measurements, are represented only for one data set.

Further analysis of the related *damping factors* gives access to the *lifetimes* of the collective modes (see Supporting Information for details). Figure 4 reports the damping factor of (A) Lysozyme solution and (B) neat D_2O as a function of pressure. The results show essentially underdamping ($0.5 < \Gamma/\Omega < 1$) for bulk water at ambient pressure over the entire Q -range within the DHO model. We note that a constant damping ratio has been imposed in the underlying fit of this data set, which was obtained from Ref. 42, while no such constraint has been used for the remaining data sets reported here. However, in pressurized D_2O this trend is unchanged in the low- Q range and the damping ratio remains < 1 . At $Q > 1.0 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ a transition towards high, close-to-critical damping ratios occurs ($\Gamma/\Omega > 1$), which even reaches critical damping ($\Gamma/\Omega = 2$) at pressures of 3 kbar for the highest Q -value. Within the simple DHO picture, this means that short wavelength pressure fluctuations ($2\pi/Q$ on the order of intermolecular distances) in compressed water (2-3 kbar) decay in an

increasingly non-oscillatory fashion with lifetimes, which are on the same order of magnitude as the period of the underlying intermolecular vibrations. Equivalently to the increase of propagation velocities, the increased dampening of short-wavelength fluctuations indicates pressure-induced structural changes in the hydrogen bond network. In the concentrated protein solution, close-to-critical damping ($\Gamma/\Omega > 1$) of short wavelength pressure fluctuations occurs already at ambient pressure. The ratio Γ/Ω at high Q-values ($Q > 1.0 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$) experiences only a small change between 1 bar and 2 kbar. However, at 3 kbar the critically damped regime is reached and the ratio Γ/Ω becomes 2 for the highest recorded Q-values, resulting in fast exponential decays of pressure fluctuations described by the fitted DHO model.

We note, that also in case of dampening of short-wavelength fluctuations, protein-induced-effects at ambient pressure resemble the properties of bulk water at elevated pressure. In addition, with increasing pressure the differences between bulk water and the protein solutions in terms of short-wavelength dampening at $Q \approx 1.3 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ decrease, equivalently to increasingly similar propagation velocities. However, the onset of critical damping for the highest pressure remains a distinct characteristic feature of the protein solutions.

To investigate in more detail the structural changes in the water hydrogen bond network with increasing pressure, we employ molecular dynamics simulations. First, we validate the simulation model by analyzing the pressure dependence of its collective properties as a function of pressure and compare it to the experimental observations. For this purpose, we utilize simulations of a deuterated multi-protein system resembling the experimental concentration of 10% w/w, which contains 5 lysozyme proteins, $\sim 30,000$ water molecules

and 40 chloride ions for charge neutralization (illustrated in Figure 5A). A bulk D₂O simulation of approximately the same size is used as reference. The collective dynamics are analyzed directly via the longitudinal current spectrum $I^{\parallel}(Q, \omega)$ obtained from space-time Fourier transformations of density currents computed from atomic velocities (see Supporting Information). The longitudinal current spectrum is directly related to the experimentally observed dynamic structure factor via $I^{\parallel}(Q, E = \hbar\omega) = (\omega^2 / Q^2) S(Q, E)$. The propagation velocities of density fluctuations are obtained equivalently to the processing of the experimental data via 1) fitting of a two DHO model for $S(Q, E)$ and 2) extracting the linear Q-dependence of the dispersive high frequency mode. We note that we limit the quantitative analysis to the determination of the frequency and propagation velocity of the dispersive high frequency mode. As an example, the longitudinal current spectrum, the frequencies of the high-frequency mode obtained from the DHO fit, and the corresponding linear fit of its Q-dependence are shown for the protein solution at a pressure of 2 kbar in Figure 5B. Propagation velocities observed for bulk water and the protein solutions are shown as a function of pressure and the corresponding density in Figures 5C and D, respectively. In qualitative agreement with the experimental results, we find increased propagation velocities in the protein solutions compared to bulk D₂O, when compared at equivalent pressures. When propagation velocities are compared as a function of the system density, the collective properties of bulk water and the protein solution describe essentially the same linear trend, which agrees with the experimental observations in the high density regime in Figure 3.

Figure 5. Molecular dynamics simulations of concentrated protein solutions. **(A)** Snapshot of the simulated system containing 5 individual proteins (colored individually) in water (red and white) with chloride ions for charge neutralization (green spheres). The blue box indicates the periodically replicated simulation cell. **(B)** Simulated longitudinal current spectrum of the protein solution at 2 kbar. Crosses indicate the Q -dependent frequency of the high frequency mode obtained from the fit between 0.3 \AA^{-1} and 1.2 \AA^{-1} . The blue dashed line shows a linear fit of the mode position. **(C)** High frequency sound velocity obtained from simulations of the protein solution and bulk D_2O as a function of pressure between 1 bar and 5 kbar. **(D)** Same as **(C)** shown as a function density observed in the respective simulation. Dashed lines in **(C)** and **(D)** indicate linear trends in the pressure- and density-dependent sound-velocity data.

While we observe some quantitative differences between simulations and experiments, the qualitative trends observed experimentally for the pressure-dependent propagation velocity are reproduced. To analyze pressure-induced structural changes in the hydration water of the protein, we refer to a second set of simulations of a single solvated protein to simplify

the analysis. Our structural analysis can be compared to previous work by Lerbret et al.¹⁹. Our simulations show that the structure of the lysozyme protein is essentially constant within simulations on the 100 ns timescale for all pressures studied here, as indicated by root mean squared deviations of non-hydrogen protein atoms (which includes sidechain motions) between 1.6 and 2.4 Å in Figure 6A. This confirms previous observations in experimental studies up to 1.5 kbar²⁰⁻²¹ and an analysis of the stability of secondary structure elements up to pressures of 6 kbar in simulations on a shorter 10 ns timescale¹⁹. To analyze structural changes in the protein hydration shell in comparison to the simulated bulk water system, we analyzed water within 5 Å from the protein surface as illustrated in Figure 6B. This included an analysis of tetrahedral order parameters q (Figure 6C), which yields 1 for a perfectly tetrahedral environment and 0 for an ideal gas⁵⁶ (see Supporting Information). We note that distributions of the q -parameter indicate two distinct sub-populations of water molecules: one with a relatively high tetrahedral order ($q=0.8$) and one with a lower tetrahedral order ($q=0.5$). Indications for both populations are observed for bulk water and protein hydration water. At ambient pressure the fraction of water molecules with low tetrahedral order is increased in protein hydration water compared to bulk water. With increasing pressure the population of water molecules with a high tetrahedral order decreases, while the fraction of water molecules with low tetrahedral order increases. This is observed in the protein hydration shell and in bulk water. However, the pressure-induced changes in the protein hydration shell are less pronounced compared to the bulk, resulting in increasingly similar distributions of the tetrahedral order parameter with increasing pressure. This is highlighted by the difference plot in the lower panel of Figure 6C. Consequently, we find that the tetrahedral structure of the hydrogen bond

network in the protein hydration shell and in bulk water becomes increasingly distorted with increasing pressure, but at the same time differences between hydration shell water and bulk water become less pronounced. The pressure-induced structural changes in bulk water observed in our simulations reproduce previous work based on numerous empirical potentials⁵⁷. Likewise, the increased similarity of bulk and protein hydration water at high pressure in terms of the orientational order quantified by q seems to be independent of the underlying water model¹⁹.

Figure 6. Molecular dynamics simulations of solvated lysozyme protein and bulk water at pressures ranging from from 1 bar to 5 kbar. **(A)** Root mean squared deviation (RMSD) of all non-hydrogen atoms of the protein from the crystal structure in 100 ns simulations. **(B)** Snapshot from the simulation of a single lysozyme molecule (grey) illustrating water molecules within 5 Å of the protein (1bar). **(C)** Distribution of the tetrahedral order parameter q in bulk water (dashed lines) and protein hydration water (solid lines; defined as water within 5 Å of the closest non-hydrogen protein atom). **(D)** Water density profiles measured as a function of distance to the protein surface (defined by distance to closest non-hydrogen protein atom). **(E)** Radial distribution functions (rdf) of water molecule centers of mass (COM) in bulk water.

To understand this observation, we analyzed the structural changes in the protein hydration shell via density profiles measured as a function of distance from the protein surface (Figure 6D). We compare our observations with radial distribution functions (rdf's) between water molecule centers of mass (COM) in bulk water simulations (Figure 6E). With increasing pressure, we find a deformation of the first peak in the protein hydration water density profile, which describes essentially the first layer of water molecules hydrating the protein surface. At ambient pressure the first peak between 2.5 and 4.0 Å is broad and shows indications of additional substructure, which we assign to the chemical heterogeneity of the protein surface, i.e. the distinct hydration of hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups. With increasing pressure, the peak narrows and its intensity increases disproportionately compared to the accompanying increase in bulk water density. This indicates a more uniform hydration of the protein surface, independent of its chemical properties. Generally, this observation agrees with the pressure-induced increased hydration of hydrophobic pockets observed previously in T4-lysozyme mutants¹⁷. A pressure-induced increase in the hydration of nonpolar atoms has also been observed in extensive simulations of the folding/unfolding equilibrium of the Trp-cage miniprotein, while the hydration of polar atoms was found insensitive to pressure⁵⁸. Changes in the relative hydration of polar and non-polar surface groups quantified by solvent accessible surface areas at pressures of 3 kbar were also reported for simulations of apomyoglobin and lysozyme⁵⁹. In addition, Figure 6D indicates an increased layering in the protein hydration shell, due to a more pronounced second peak, which increases in amplitude and changes its position from ~6.5 Å at 1 bar to ~6.0 Å at 5 kbar.

Pressure-induced changes in the bulk water structure as described by the rdf's in Figure 6E show qualitatively distinct characteristics, which are in accord with experimental data⁶⁰. The narrow first peak, describing the first shell of neighboring water molecules, is essentially unchanged with increasing pressure. Hence, the oxygen-oxygen distance of water-water hydrogen bonds is roughly pressure-independent. The structural response to increasing pressure mainly affects the first minimum and the second peak of the rdf, representing interstitial water and the second hydration shell, respectively. Both features are clearly resolved at ambient pressure. However, with increasing pressure water molecules from the second hydration shell penetrate into the interstitial region as a primary elastic response to compression, hence increasing the packing density of water itself⁶⁰⁻⁶¹. The observations in Figures 6D and E explain the distinct behavior of the tetrahedral order parameters as a function of pressure in the protein environment and in pure water. In case of the protein hydration shell, the main elastic response to pressure-induced compression is the increased hydration of the protein surface, which requires a less pronounced change in the water hydrogen bond network structure. In bulk water this predetermined breaking point is absent and high pressures result in more pronounced changes in the tetrahedral hydrogen bond network structure, mainly affecting hydrogen bond angles and not hydrogen bond lengths.

Generally, we recognize in this study that the water structure and collective dynamics are distinct in the protein hydration shell and bulk water, which is reflected here by the difference in pressure-induced changes in collective dynamics. Our findings indicate that the tetrahedral order of the water hydrogen bond network may be tightly linked to the high frequency collective properties of water and protein solutions. Both, experimentally

observed propagation velocities and short wavelength damping coefficients are increased in protein solutions compared to bulk water of equivalent pressure, in qualitative agreement with the decreased tetrahedral order of the water hydrogen bond network in the protein hydration shell. Likewise, differences between the collective properties of protein solutions and bulk water decrease with increasing pressure, akin to the increased similarity of the tetrahedral order parameter distributions in Figure 6C.

Increased propagation velocities indicate increasingly solid/glass-like properties of the water hydrogen bond network with increasing pressure and packing density. In experiments and simulations alike, the propagation velocities are roughly proportional to the total density of the system and seem relatively independent of the system composition (Figures 3 and 5D). Protein solutions at ambient pressure, with an increased overall density and a protein-induced decrease of the tetrahedral order in the water hydrogen bond network, exhibit collective dynamics that can be qualitatively compared to bulk water at increased pressures with an equivalent overall density. With increasing pressure, the overall densities and fast sound propagation velocities become increasingly similar between protein solutions and pure water, due to distinct pressure-induced changes in the water hydrogen bond network structure.

However, we also note a qualitative difference in the pressure-response of collective properties with and without solvated proteins. The onset of high dampening coefficients Γ , i.e. the occurrence of damping ratios $\Gamma/\Omega > 1$ at intermediate wavelengths, i.e. $Q < 1.0 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ (Figure 4A), indicating increasingly non-oscillatory dynamics, is only observed for the protein solutions and occurs simultaneously with an increased hydration of the protein surface (Figure 6D). Likewise, the damping of short-wavelength fluctuations ($Q > 1.0 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$)

remains significantly more pronounced in protein solutions compared to bulk water, also at high pressures or equivalent densities. While it is difficult to provide a detailed microscopic interpretation of the damping of collective modes obtained in the fit of the DHO model, we recall the occurrence of a slowdown of protein dynamics as a response to increased pressure²⁰. Pressure induces an increase in hydration of the protein surface and therefore results in altered properties of the average protein-water interface in the solution. We may speculate that the observation of enhanced damping of collective modes in protein solutions and a slowdown of protein dynamics are related to each other, as the dynamics of system components are coupled via the altered protein-water interface. Interactions between the protein and water at the biomolecular interface play an important role for the coupling of vibrational modes between both components. In previous simulations of hydrated protein crystals, it could be shown that collective modes, characteristic of the protein, propagate into the surrounding hydration water⁶². Likewise, correlated protein-water vibrations and resulting collective modes were shown to depend on the chemical properties of the protein-water interface⁶³⁻⁶⁴.

Promising future extensions of our studies involve simultaneous variations in temperature and pressure. Raman spectroscopy studies of lysozyme solutions suggest that increased, non-denaturing pressures are able to reverse structural changes involved in early stages of thermal denaturation⁶⁵. Such pressure-induced suppressions of conformational fluctuations are likely to also affect picosecond timescale, collective dynamics in the protein and its dynamical coupling to the surrounding water hydrogen bond network.

Conclusion

In summary, this study investigates the pressure dependence of structural properties and collective dynamics in water and protein solutions for moderate, non-denaturing pressures between 1 bar and 3 kbar (up to 5 kbar in the simulations). We find that protein hydration water exhibits some features of pressurized water and that with increasing pressure and density, differences in the water hydrogen bond network structure and collective dynamics largely decrease, apart from critical damping of collective modes, which only occurs in protein solutions.

Previous experimental studies have shown that high-frequency sound propagation velocities between various biomolecular systems (protein or peptide solutions, living cells) are roughly comparable at ambient pressures, while fitted damping factors of the collective modes often exhibit distinct Q-dependent behavior⁵³. Here, we add external pressure as an additional variable and observe distinct pressure-induced changes of high-frequency sound velocities and damping factors in absence or presence of solvated proteins. However, the overall density seems to remain the main factor influencing collective mode propagation on the experimental timescale, while the specific interactions between the solvated protein surface and the hydration shell, as well as also the collective properties of the proteins themselves, seem to affect the damping.

In total, we find that pressure-induced changes of collective dynamics provide a promising probe to study the hydration of biomolecules, providing information also relevant for ambient conditions, i.e. via the pressure-dependent hydration of the heterogeneous protein surface. Ambient pressure collective dynamics of various biological samples are currently an active field of research. In this context, it is essential to be able to provide microscopic interpretations for the available experimental observables, such as sound propagation

velocities and damping. This combined experimental and theoretical study provides a crucial step along those lines, as the pressure-dependence allows us to analyze the influence of structural changes in the water hydrogen bond network, either due to interaction with a solvated biomolecule or pressure, on the experimentally accessible properties.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supplementary material (sample preparation, High Pressure Cell set up, Brillouin neutron scattering experiment, data analysis, DHO model, molecular dynamics protocol, protein stability, protein protonation states) is available.

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Notes

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TOC:

Longitudinal current spectra in lysozyme solutions.